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Study of Pharmaceutical Marketing Strategies

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ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical companies design different marketing strategies based on market demand and requirements in the pharmaceutical industry. Leading pharmaceutical companies are using Good marketing strategies based on market research which helps companies make successful but these companies can't design proper marketing strategies or innovate in products and processes, making it difficult for them to compete with leading organizations in the pharmaceutical industry that are embracing innovation. The pharmaceutical industry is highly advanced and innovative there are big giant companies that lot invest in their product development processes and technologies but many companies and industries challenges facing introducing a product and gating market share in the market even make a success of this new product launch sales with different marketing efforts (strategies, support) So in this thesis researcher want to understand the development of

marketing initiative, strategies, campaigns and their gaps because designing strategies are highly costly and timeconsuming so the right strategy of marketing help companies to get success in the pharmaceutical industry Researchers try to discuss the right analyses processes of strategies and their outcomes of pharmaceutical marketing strategies which help to get success pharmaceutical companies After studying marketing strategy which are the right strategies and which are improvements required, that will more effective and successful in the pharmaceutical marketing industry. The researcher collected a questionnaire from 60 respondents and out of 60 (41 respondents)

give responses on Google from convenience sampling with different locations in Maharashtra to understand different strategies important and their gaps also take customers feedback on marketing support, strategies and tools. As pharmaceutical firms shift from one marketing strategy to another, we will present a study on the shifting marketing strategies of pharma companies. It will also provide insight into the different marketing tools and strategies employed by pharmaceutical companies.

INTRODUCTION

Indian Pharmaceutical Industry and Scope

Indian pharmaceutical industry is one of the growing industry's in the world and India is the hub of the world largest manufacturer companies hub and in us dollar 40 billion by value, the world's 3rd largest by overall volume in the world. Indian pharmaceutical industry largest provider of generic drugs (20%) to the world and the Indian pharmaceutical industry total export of pharmaceutical drugs (3.5%) to more than 150 countries. In India day by day healthcare product demand increasing with the growing economy of India life expectancy of the Indian population increasing. So most of the companies taking initiative to expand business in the Indian market by providing economical generic drug. Major pharmaceutical manufacturing hub in India in the following cities Aurangabad, Pune, Baddi, Hyderabad, Chennai, Kolkata, Ahmedabad.

Government Initiative

Indian government encourage pharmaceutical companies to expand their manufacturing capacities and invent new drugs (cancer, AIDS, Covide19,) Most of the states in India provide facilities to manufacturing units to make a setup in their state (Goa, Uttaranchal, Sikkim)

Largest pharmaceutical companies of India as per below data

Table1.1 Pharmaceutical Companies in India

Rank	Company	Market Capitalization August 2021 (INRcrores)
1	Sun Pharma ltd	182,469INR
2	Divi's Laboratories ltd	128,794INR
2	Reddy's Laboratories Hyderabad	75,113INR
4	CiplaltdMumbai	73,042INR
5	GlandPharmaltd	64,163INR
6	CadilaHealthcareltd	55,727INR
7	Torrent PharmaceuticalsLtd	51,927INR
8	AlkemLaboratoriesltd	45,759INR
9	Lupinpharmaceuticalltd	41,917INR
10	Aurobindo Pharmacompany	39,328INR

Importance of marketing strategy observation (analysis)

An important part of marketing strategy is monitoring and evaluating market needs. An analysis of the strategy required to determine the suitability of products or services within a market and how to determine the product quality and the product reach. More over, marketing strategy focuses on the behaviour of consumers and on their purchasing activities.

The purpose of marketing studies is to gain a better understanding of opportunities within a specific market, to find out what your customers think of your products, to improve your communication and messaging platforms with your clients. An important element of improving customer satisfaction is to understand what factors affect your marketing strategy. Below is a list of questions to ask yourself as you analyze your marketing efforts.

- Study of the pharmaceutical industry market and customers behaviour
- The Study of the pharmaceutical industry help to design an effective marketing strategy

According to the sub-title, what is the difference between these two terms? The pharmaceutical industry is always focusing on the 'market' or 'marketing,' and marketing studies are like a subset of market analysis and study which helps with marketing

Nature and Scope of Research of Pharmaceutical Marketing Strategies

Scope of marketing strategy analysis:-

There are two different terminology systems. The purpose of pharmaceutical marketing and marketing strategy analysis is to gather and analyze data within a target segment, area, or market. Collection of data is the basis for both. In any case, the type of data to be gathered depends on the analysis. An analysis of the market or a marketing study focusing on marketing and strategy is required. In the study or analysis, selecting a segment that is relevant to a business goal depends on the business and the industry rather than doing the full marketing analysis based on industry need.

Table 1.2 Marketing Strategies

	Market research	
	Marketing Analysis	Entry in market and Exit from market
Industry analysis	Marketing strategy Study and gaps	Market regulation and feedback
	Marketing strategy implication	

With the changing client's ways of behaving the development in economy and variety, having atop to bottom information on how your market works is a tough spot and there are difficulties. At present efficiently doing promoting Studies and assembling specialists for business advancement in the showcasing and their systems of organization's items, administrations. Techniques Organizations need to guarantee that advertising methodologies perform as indicated by the prerequisite of market and their assumptions drug organization's business objectives, key components to doing a promoting investigation.

A Study of the market and target clients

Albeit an advertising Study has a more extensive degree, organizations need to lead this Study well defined for business sectors and clients. This gathering of clients will turn into the objective or master on your advertisements and special technique Item and cost investigation: This examination manages the valuing of the item in another market or the improvement of the item presence in a current market. Utilize the system to figure out your clients' thought process of your item estimating. An assess the evaluating information, and observe improvement in valuing technique which help to contend in the current market and at the cost, it ought to straight way of behaving of target clients. There are a few components to think about while deciding value, it should likewise be possible involving three evaluating systems in the business in light of study (plot, free amount, Credit note) these are estimating rehearses in the drug business. Promoting investigation: Advertisement is the most common way of making attention to items and organizations and administrations through promotions. Promotions can either be shown on the web or disconnected. The viable technique elevates adding to significant clients. For the examination, you really want to decide how your advertisement are acting concerning click if on the web, and the quantity of reactions from individuals if disconnected.

Deals information examination: For previously existing items, the business Studies will assist with getting significant information about your evaluating technique either by changing them or offering limits. Concentrate on shows a total piece of items that are not getting income but rather income creating items help Pharma organizations so organizations need to intently break down information of performing and non-performing items for income age a marketing chart, look at this bit by bit deals report. It very well might be valuable to at what stage need to investigation

Advancement examination: Promotional Study is a strategy utilized in assessing the exhibition of special offers is accessible restricted period and this is the technique for methodologies Doing this Study gives a comprehension of the past advancements, which can be utilized for working on future advancements. All the more explicitly, a piece of Studies is utilized to decide the effect of advancement on deals and the disposition of clients towards marked down costs.

Appropriation channel: circulation is significant advertising procedures it assists with finding and interface with clients. Appropriation examination figures out which directs will be utilized in conveying organization items or administrations to likely clients. Drug circulation is done through stock room, CNF, drug stores and production line out let Successful showcasing procedure investigation can assist the organization with defeating missteps and improvement in industry execution on all boundary

Aim and Objective of Study

Researcher study analyses the processes and outcomes of pharmaceutical marketing strategies and which are the right strategies that will be more effective and successful in the pharmaceutical marketing industry.

In this study, we will look at how pharmaceutical companies are shifting their marketing strategies from one strategy to another. Additionally, this study will provide an insight into the different marketing tools and strategies used by pharmaceutical companies (e.g., supply chain processes, pricing strategies, and marketing input utilization, along with a brief description of the customer perceptions based on which organizations are framing their marketing strategies).

- The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of Place Strategies on stakeholder satisfaction and sales.

LITERATURE REVIEW

By emphasizing the geographic origin, or location of production, of the product's primary ingredient(s), numerous businesses, including wine producers, have successfully communicated the nature of their products to the market. The purpose of this article is to: elucidate the concept of a "place-based" advertising strategy, also known as a system of advertising that associates a product with a specific geographical region; explain why it is so important to the wine industry; Moreover, there are a number of reasons why it might be superior to other kinds of marketing

strategies for certain kinds of products, such as protective gear and replacement parts. For instance, since the demand for these products in the city is extremely high and the demand in the provincial market is extremely low, businesses need to adapt their marketing strategies to the geological conditions in which they operate (Thode, S. F., & Maskulka, J. M., 1998). Vineyard valuation, place-based marketing strategies, and brand equity. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, Many businesses, including wine producers, have successfully communicated the nature of their products to the market by emphasizing the geographic origin, or place of production, of the product's primary ingredient(s). The purpose of this article is to: elucidate the concept of a "place-based" advertising strategy, also known as a system of advertising that associates a product with a specific geographical region; explain why it is so important to the wine industry; Moreover, there are a number of reasons why it might be superior to other forms of advertising for particular kinds of goods, such as protective items and replacement gear. For instance, since the demand for these goods in the city is extremely high and the demand in the provincial market is extremely low, businesses need to adapt their development strategies to the geological conditions in which they operate (Thode, S. F., & Maskulka, J. M., 1998). Vineyard valuation, place-based marketing strategies, and brand equity. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*: Drug store and business behaviors are not valued by both parties in the drug industry. These are typical, to be expected events that are crucial to any business's efforts to achieve success in terms of deal development and profit. The article infers that possibly information about the effect that our choices and actions have on others may, in some small way, contribute to growing more dissemination channel-accommodating practices by referring to a few models from the two perspectives. Information on the corona impact of their activities could smooth a necessary and fundamental relationship, but investors can expect the two elements to be around for a long time. A. Wertheimer (2008) The medication business has had various achievements in its treatment of crafted by craftsmanship "4 P's." Concerning the "item," the drug testing and assembling organizations have long recognized the significance of the advertising concept, which focuses on the omitted social needs. While the pharmaceutical industry's commitments to society regarding the disclosure of new drugs are undeniable, the company has engaged in a variety of different activities, each designed to improve its product for a specific customer. The drug industry's efforts have significantly altered how medical services, regardless of whether a prescription is present, are evaluated. The appropriation framework in use in this industry is a clear commitment to promoting frameworks. With the utmost skill,

items can be delivered to virtually any location within the framework's spans in approximately 24 hours. There are a variety of patient assistance programs supported by pharmaceutical companies. Each of these projects offers a chance to educate the patient while simultaneously serving as an asset to wholesalers, delegates, and doctors, and one can quickly see the likely benefits. Additional restricted time tries meriting notice consolidate data base advancing and benefits exhibiting. While the benefits of these practices have not been totally recognized in the cure market, each tends to a colossal opportunity for the business. Even though it would appear that there are a few instances of genuine commitment or advancement in the drug industry in such a way, the industry ought to be praised for its effective use of advertising strategies and ideas developed by and implemented by other businesses. D. McCaffrey (2002)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND ANALYSIS

Data Analysis

1) Which is the best marketing toll as per you?

41 responses

Interpretation

In these questionnaires, the researcher tries to find more about effective marketing tool

After conducting research we see pie chart result based on survey out of 41 respondents 43% respondents accept price is the best tool of marketing and these tool is company promotion 26.8% of respondents accept this.

3) Which channels do your buyers use to learn about new products, gather information recommendation or make purchases?

41 responses

Interpretation

Regarding offline and online marketing strategy 51.2% of respondents accept they received information of brand off line through (doctor, chemist, and Medical rep)

4) Have you seen any pharmaceutical advertisement on social media?

41 responses

Interpretation

68% of respondents accept the seenads related to the pharmaceutical brands on social media

5) Which types of healthcare marketing campaigns are more likely to be successful in pharmaceutical industry?

41 responses

Interpretation

In this pichart, we find 43.9% of participants believe in scientific promotion which is highest than the input distribution strategy.

6) In pharmaceutical industry low pricing of medicines gives any impact on sale ?

41 responses

Interpretation

In this pichart, we find 95.1% of participants believe in pharmaceutical industry low pricing of medicines have impacton their sales.

7) Will Customer recognise pharmaceutical product features in terms of color, branding and logo.

41 responses

Interpretation

In the 7th question researcher ask question about the product features colour, branding and logo in this question 87.8% of respondents accept brand, logo, colouris important,

8) Will you agree with the fact that pharmaceutical products with process patent was an important factor for growth of the Indian companies?

41 responses

Interpretation

In the 8th question, the researcher ask about the patent process of pharmaceutical companies which is help add value to the growth of the product in this question 90.02 respondent accept patent process is important for growth.

9) Do you agree with the point that doctors spare time to the companies as per the relationship with company's medical representative?

41 responses

Interpretation

In researcher ask about the role of medical representative making relation with doctors and doctors give time a pharmamedical representative based on his relation

10) Operation in less attractive therapeutic segment or category can be a reason of stagnancy for the companies?

41 responses

Interpretation

10th question researcher asks about less attractive segment and discusses less attractive segment reason for business stagnancy in this question 92.7% respondent accept this fact product is more important.

11) Do you agree companies' sales force play an important role in capturing better market share for companies?

41 responses

Interpretation

The researcher asks the 11th question about marketing strategy and campaign implementation by medical representative and any role of medical representative in campaign implementation

In this question, 97.6% of respondents accept medical representatives play important role in campaign execution and sales developing

12) For sustainable growth, which is the most important market for the companies in Indian context?

41 responses

Interpretation

Most participants accept this question rural as well as urban both markets is important for growth in the Indian market

13) Effective supply chain management ,product and services help to generate sales of pharmaceutical companies.

41 responses

Interpretation

In the 13th question, there researcher asks a question about researcher supply chain management and product service. On this question, 97.6% respondent supply chain is a very important part of pharmaceutical industry sales growth.

14) Adaptation of pharmaceutical marketing strategy changes with geographical location

41 responses

Interpretation

In this question, the Researcher asks about marketing strategies and their changes based on geographical location and situation on market. 82.9% of respondents accept can marketing strategies based on geographical location and 17.1% of respondents say there is no need to change marketing strategy based on geographical location.

15) Which pharmaceutical medicine mostly preferred by customer?

41 responses

Interpretation

In this question, the researcher asks about branded vs generic medicine and their preference for choosing a brand generic or branded. In this question, 85.4% of respondents accept branded drugs they have buying preference instead of generic 14.6 % of respondents choose the option of the generic drug as buying preference.

CONCLUSION

After Study of pharmaceutical marketing strategies and suggest different strategies in discussion to improve effective marketing, companies need to adopt digital marketing or digital device for marketing (TAB) effective survey and feed back through digital platforms play important role in implicated marketing strategies. Regular turning of the medical representative is required for effective communication and strategy implementation in the industry, Supply chain pricing strategy needs to change as per area requirement it will add values in sales development. Supply chain pricing strategy needs to change as per area requirement it will add values in sales development New product development and upgrading of products are required in the pharmaceutical industry to play important role in sales development and revenue generation.

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